

Specific Features of Using Problem-Based Learning in Teaching Foreign Language Teaching

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Abstract:

The problem solving teaching method is a popular approach to learning that allows students to understand new concepts in practice. This approach provides students with examples and real-world situations so they can see how the theory behind a concept or skill works in practice.

Keywords: educational process, memorize, cognitive, problem-based learning, problem situation.

Currently, in the educational process, teachers are increasingly using such a way of organizing student activities as problem-based learning, which can be interpreted as a system of teaching methods in which students acquire knowledge not by memorizing and memorizing them in a ready-made form, but as a result of mental work to solve problems and problematic tasks based on the content of the material being studied.

One of the categories of problem-based learning is a problematic situation, which is a cognitive difficulty, to overcome which students must acquire new knowledge or make intellectual efforts. This is an intellectual difficulty of the student, which prevents him from immediately solving a cognitive or practical task, requiring the search for new knowledge or new ways of acting to remove the difficulty. Problematic situations can be objective (the situation is set by the teacher) and subjective (the psychological state of intellectual difficulty in solving the problem). There are also four interrelated functions of the problem situation: a) stimulating; b) educational; c) organizing; d) controlling.

Since problem-based learning involves a strictly thought-out system of problem situations, problems and tasks corresponding to the cognitive capabilities of the trainees, the following levels of complexity can be distinguished:

- 1st level - the teacher analyzes the problem situation, identifies the problem, formulates the task and directs the trainees to independent finding solutions;
- 2nd level – the difference is that the teacher analyzes the situation together with the students, bringing them to the problem, and the students independently formulate the task and solve it;
- 3rd level (the highest) – the teacher brings to the students the content of the problem situation, its analysis, identification of the problem, formulation of the problem and the choice of the optimal solution, the students carry out independently.

In solving the educational and developmental tasks of problem-based learning, the problem situation is the central link. The success of the educational and cognitive process largely depends on how well it was created. Therefore, the basis for pedagogical guidance of problem-based learning of students should be the setting of a sequential series of progressively more complex mental tasks and teaching them how to solve them. It is also necessary to adhere to the following pedagogical requirements for creating problematic situations:

- create problematic situations based on real life material, both historical, described in literature, and modern;
- to design a problem situation in such a way that its content corresponds to the theoretical knowledge of the students.

If students do not have any basic theoretical knowledge, then it is necessary to fill in the missing knowledge through explanations before students begin to solve the problem:

- always build a problematic situation on familiar educational material that has not been analyzed before;
- problematic situations are necessarily based on the students' specific practical experience;
- Formulate questions in such a way that they are really problematic and exclude any attempt to answer with memorized material and require independent thinking. For example, when studying. The topic "Achievements of science and technology" can be offered to students a problematic situation: "How do technology and mass media contribute to the interpenetration of cultures?";
- when drawing up problem questions, it is necessary to follow the rule: all questions should require either an explanation of certain phenomena from the point of view ("why?", "what explains?", "what is the reason?", etc.), or proof, theoretical justification of the truth of known (studied in this topic) provisions. The experience of teachers shows that in traditional lessons students are rarely involved in truly creative work, do not train the ability to solve complex problems on their own, most often they receive knowledge in a ready-made form, memorize it and reproduce it. That is why problematic situations in lessons are so necessary, which make you think, look for answers, and personally understand facts and events. Among the active teaching methods in which problematic situations are present, it is possible to distinguish. A discussion method that is used to share experiences between students, to clarify and coordinate the positions of all participants in the discussion, to develop a unified approach to analyzing a certain phenomenon. The discussion has a certain dynamics, in which three stages are clearly distinguished: the beginning, collective discussion, and summing up. The discussion needs to be well organized, so it is necessary to make a plan for its holding in advance. As a rule, it is necessary to outline:
 - several key issues and blocks (3-4 additional, private ones each questions for each node), which cover the main content of the topic;

- an introduction aimed at starting a discussion;
- the main arguments and theses that will be the main guideline during the discussion;
- tasks for the most advanced students to perform the role of opponents in a number of key positions. Sometimes the main issues can be framed in the form of special schemes in which only one of the three or four provisions is correct. Experience suggests that the method of educational discussions improves and strengthens knowledge, increases the volume of new information, develops the ability to argue, to prove, defend and defend your opinion and listen to the opinion of others.

The round table method is a collective exchange of opinions, a joint search for truth at the round table, which is one of the most effective teaching methods, especially at the senior stage of training.

- A business game is a pedagogical technique for modeling various situations aimed at teaching students how to make decisions. Classes in the form of a business game significantly activate the educational process, evoke a spirit of rivalry, emotional intensity, contribute to the development of creative thinking of students, teach them to purposefully apply existing knowledge in practice. Business Game it consists of 3 stages: preparation for the game (defining the goals of the game, developing the rules of the game, defining and distributing roles taking into account the individual characteristics of students, thinking over evaluation criteria, methodological and material support of the game, determining tasks for self-preparation, timing, theoretical preparation), conducting a business game, summing up.

Intellectual assault – the essence of this method is the collective search for non-traditional ways to solve the problem that has arisen, which contributes to a better formation students have communicative skills that are necessary for communication in the educational and labor sphere. Also, "intellectual assault" develops the ability to independently find and use the necessary information, develops the skill of mutual control and self-control, as well as improves such moral qualities as mutual assistance, tolerance, cooperation. Analysis of specific situations is the most effective technique at all stages of education, starting from elementary school. The advantage of this method is that in the classroom there is a unique opportunity to create specific problem situations taken from school, household or family practice. Students participate with special enthusiasm in analyzing the situation and make optimal decisions, since the topics are very close and understandable, and therefore interesting and relevant. Depending on the topic of the lesson and the specifics of the content of the material, various types of situations can be used in the classroom:

- situations-illustrations where the teacher gives an example from school practice or his personal experience;
- Assessment situations where students are offered a description of a specific action. The task of the students is to assess the significance of the situation and the correctness of the actions of the students. For example, a specific case is proposed for analysis (a conflict situation between classmates in the dining room and appropriate measures on the part of the canteen attendant). Students analyze the situation, evaluate the correctness of actions and offer their own option; Analysis of specific situations is the most effective technique at all stages of education, starting from elementary school. The advantage of this method is that in the classroom there is a unique opportunity to create specific problem situations taken from school, household or family practice. Students participate with special enthusiasm in analyzing the situation and make optimal decisions, since the topics are very close and understandable, and therefore interesting and relevant [4]. Depending on the topic of the lesson and the specifics of the content of the material, various types of situations can be used in the classroom:

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The task of the students is to assess the significance of the situation and the correctness of the actions of the students. For example, a specific case is proposed for analysis (a conflict situation between classmates in the dining room and appropriate measures on the part of the canteen attendant). Students analyze the situation, evaluate the correctness of actions and offer their own version; situations are exercises that imply that students they do a little research in the classroom. For example, each student gets a task – to conduct research in a group (how much time they spend watching TV, what are their favorite programs, etc.), interview other students, fill out a table, analyze the results, draw a conclusion and give advice or share their experience. I would also like to note that problem-based learning in English lessons creates an atmosphere of relaxed communication. Problem -based learning in English lessons is more effective when problematic issues are addressed to the student himself and involve the use of his life experience (family relationships, hobbies, problems of teenagers). Work experience also shows that it is possible to bring problematic issues closer to the conditions of real communication not only due to the vitality of situations, but also by increasing the novelty of information, and this undoubtedly arouses interest in them. For example, an evening is planned in the classroom, and the teacher can start the lesson not with the current material, but offer to express his plans for its implementation, prompting students to find the words they need, and offer their ideas. It should be noted that during the discussion you should not stop the guys to analyze language errors, but simply correct them without disrupting the discussion. When repeating any If there is a language error, you need to take note of it and conduct the necessary training exercises in the next lesson. Based on all of the above, it can be concluded that a problematic situation stimulates the speech activity of students, increases the volume and variety of forms of utterance, and also contributes to the strength of the formed speech skills and abilities. Moreover, using problematic situations in foreign language teaching classes. It becomes obvious that a small vocabulary is not an obstacle to expressing thoughts in a foreign language, and this supports interest in a foreign language. Experience shows that problematic situations, as close as possible to real life, increase the effectiveness of the lesson, activate the speech activity of students, arouse their interest in a foreign language, and, as a result, the overall academic performance of students improves.

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